

A Literature Review of AI-Based Multilingual and Multimodal Fake News Detection

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to synthesize existing literature on AI-based fake news detection to inform the development of a tailored platform to mitigate misinformation in Sri Lankan social media contexts. The rapid proliferation of fake news and deepfake content on social media platforms poses a significant threat to information credibility, particularly in Sri Lanka, where social media usage is surging. This study proposes an AI-based platform tailored to detect fake news among Sri Lankan social media users, integrating image-based machine learning and text-based natural language processing (NLP) models to provide real-time feedback through a recommendation system. This literature review synthesizes existing research on fake news detection, focusing on three key areas: factors contributing to the creation and spread of misinformation, machine learning and deep learning techniques (e.g., CNN, RNN, LSTM, BERT, SVM, KNN) to detect fake news and deepfakes, and evaluation approaches to assess content authenticity. The review highlights the effectiveness of deep learning models like LSTM and BERT in capturing complex textual patterns and CNNs for image analysis, while traditional methods like SVM rely on feature engineering. Critical research gaps include the lack of Sri Lanka-specific datasets, limited studies on multilingual (Sinhala/Tamil/English) misinformation detection, and the need for hybrid multimodal models. The proposed platform addresses these gaps by leveraging a dataset from Kegalle, combining true and fake news, and developing a custom model for real-time detection. This study aims to deliver a locally adapted, accurate, and user-friendly solution to mitigate misinformation in Sri Lankan social media contexts, contributing to enhanced digital trust and societal stability.

Keywords: *Multilingual, Multimodal, Fake News Detection, Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Processing*